

Leibniz Collaborative Excellence Project ML4SIM

Tim Schmidt; Stefano Cassola; Miro Duhovic; David May
(Patrick Nowakowski)

Weierstraß-Institut für
Angewandte Analysis und Stochastik

Leibniz-Institut
für Polymerforschung
Dresden

Fraunhofer
ITWM

Deutsches Forschungszentrum
für Künstliche Intelligenz
German Research Center for
Artificial Intelligence

Leibniz-Institut für
Verbundwerkstoffe

The Project Team

„ML4ProcessSimulation - Machine Learning for Simulation Intelligence in Composite Process Design“

is funded by the Leibniz Association within the Leibniz Collaborative Excellence funding programme (funding reference: K377/2021)

Associated partners
(for int. exchange)

UNIVERSITY OF DELAWARE
Prof. Suresh Advani

UNIVERSITY of WASHINGTON
Prof. J. Nathan Kutz

What is Multiscale Bridging?

Composites process simulation relies on simplification, homogenization and scale separation

Scale separation This topic is very complex and raises many questions:

- Do we need the microscale?
- If we need the microscale, do we need to separate the micro- and mesoscale levels?
- If we consider the scale levels separately, how do we unify them again?

Multiscale Bridging Methods

How is the microscale taken into account for mesoscopic permeability determination?

- 1) **Simple scale-up method**
(homogenized microscale permeability)
- vs.
- 2) **Scale-bridging method**
(local microscale permeability)
- vs.
- 3) **Fully resolved models**
(no scale separation)

Model Generation & Flow Simulation

Creation of layers

Random stacking & cropping of free edges

Compression

Flow simulation

Geometrical models / statistical representative volume elements (SVE)

Layer size	3x3 rovings
No. of layers	6
Voxel size	6 ³ μm ³
No. of randomized models	12

Permeability prediction

Software	GeoDict (FlowDict)
Solver	LIR-Solver (FRM) ^{*1} SimpleFFT-Solver (SUM & SBM) ^{*2}
Flow model	Stokes ^{*1} Stokes-Brinkman ^{*2}
Boundary conditions	tangential: periodic
	flow dir.: periodic, in- & outlet 40 voxel
	Pressure drop: 1 Pa

*1) No porous structure > faster LIR solver & Stokes is possible

*2) Consideration of anisotropic microscale permeability only with Stokes-Brinkman & SimpleFFT

Simple Scale-up Method (SUM)

Material-ID 01

Material-ID 02

ID	Name	Perm. X / (m ²)	Perm. Y / (m ²)	Perm. Z / (m ²)
00	Fluid...	-	-	-
01	Fluid in Porous [Weft]...	6.9E-13	2.8E-15	4.4E-15
02	Fluid in Porous [Warp]...	2.8E-15	6.9E-13	4.4E-15

Scale-Bridging Method (SBM)

1. Scale-down from mesoscale to microscale

- Segmentation of the rovings
- Analysis of the roving segments (roving cross section & roving orientation)
- Derivation of the microscopic characteristics (FVC & fiber orientation)

2. Scale-up from micro- to mesoscale

- AI-based permeability prediction from derived microscopic characteristics [1, 2]
- Assign microscale permeability to the rovings segments in the mesoscale model
- Numerical permeability prediction of the mesoscale model

[1] Schmidt, T. D.K. Natarajan, et al., Geometric Model Dataset and Machine Learning Models for Permeability Prediction of Fibrous Structures, 2024, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4872087

[2] Schmidt, T., Cassola, S., Duhovic, M., May, D.(IVW). (2023). Numerically predicted permeability of over 6500 artificially generated fibrous microstructures [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10047095>

Fully resolved models (FRM)

Geometrical models:

Layer size	2.4 x 2.4 rovings
No. of layers	4
Voxel size	$1^3 \mu\text{m}^3$
No. of randomized models	3

- Microscale permeability doesn't need to be considered via parameters, as the structure is mapped

Comparison of the Results

Method	Model name	SVP in %	FVC in %		K11 in m ²		K22 in m ²		K33 in m ²		Runtime in h	Model size in voxel			Voxel edge length in μm
		MV	MV	SD	MV	CV	MV	CV	MV	CV		MV	CV	X-axis MV	
SUM	SUM70	70,4	38,9	0,23	1,78E-10	11%	1,73E-10	12%	1,37E-11	30%	10,5	1167	1143	286	6
	SUM75	75,5	41,4	0,26	1,09E-10	25%	1,11E-10	19%	8,11E-12	41%	8,4	1156	1174	267	6
	SUM80	80,6	45,0	0,28	5,76E-11	22%	6,73E-11	17%	4,59E-12	97%	5,9	1181	1144	249	6
	SUM85	85,6	49,4	0,28	2,25E-11	68%	3,20E-11	39%	1,95E-12	77%	5,9	1195	1183	230	6
	SUM90	90,6	56,5	0,28	4,31E-12	72%	8,40E-12	76%	6,16E-13	158%	5,9	1195	1183	215	6
SBM	SBM70	70,4	38,9	0,23	1,76E-10	10%	1,71E-10	13%	1,35E-11	31%	9,0	1167	1143	286	6
	SBM75	75,5	41,4	0,26	1,10E-10	24%	1,12E-10	19%	8,19E-12	40%	7,9	1156	1174	267	6
	SBM80	80,6	45,0	0,28	5,86E-11	21%	6,84E-11	17%	4,68E-12	95%	6,3	1181	1144	249	6
	SBM85	85,6	49,4	0,28	2,34E-11	65%	3,29E-11	38%	2,00E-12	78%	4,9	1195	1183	230	6
	SBM90	90,6	56,5	0,36	5,08E-12	63%	9,38E-12	64%	5,15E-13	148%	3,8	1177	1156	215	6
FRM	Comp20	42,7	0,06	1,65E-10	4%	1,35E-10	11%	1,08E-11	18%	98,5	5100	5100	1007	1	
	Comp30	48,1	0,03	1,23E-10	4%	1,01E-10	15%	7,67E-12	7%	113,1	5100	5100	895	1	
	Comp33	49,9	0,10	1,09E-10	5%	8,80E-11	13%	5,70E-12	20%	88,4	5100	5100	861	1	
	Comp40	55,0	0,11	5,87E-11	7%	5,87E-11	16%	3,43E-12	24%	97,6	5100	5100	783	1	
	Comp46	60,2	0,03	4,78E-11	3%	3,47E-11	25%	2,44E-12	25%	99,4	5100	5100	716	1	

Comparison of in-plane results

- SBM & SUM permeability values and CV are comparable - no significant difference can be recognized
- FRM permeability values significantly higher than SUM and SBM
- Experimental results are lower and decrease more slowly with increasing FVC compared to SUM & SBM

Outlook

Multiscale Bridging: The computational effort, permeability values and scattering of results are comparable for SUM and SBM scale bridging methods

- SBM can also be carried out without AI, but with a microscale permeability database.
- SBM takes more details into account and is therefore more accurate, but the effect will probably only really come into play at very high FVCs when the microscale permeability dominates.
- SUM and SBM tested with other materials and at higher FVCs (>56.5%)

More Experiments: More complex unsaturated two-phase simulations require characterization of the dynamic wetting contact angle

- Further development of a dynamic wetting contact angle testing rig
- Further out-of-plane permeability measurements

Acknowledgements

„ML4ProcessSimulation - Machine Learning for Simulation Intelligence in Composite Process Design“

is funded by the Leibniz Association within the Leibniz Collaborative Excellence funding programme (funding reference: K377/2021)

gefördert durch

Leibniz
Leibniz-
Wettbewerb

